

FERTILITY LEVEL, TRENDS AND BEHAVIOUR IN NIGERIA

Akinokun Rilwan Akintayo^{1*} and Abidoeye Oyekunle Muritala²

¹*Department of Demography and Social Statistics, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria*

²*Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Federal Polytechnic, Zamfara, Nigeria*

*Corresponding author email: akinokunridwan@gmail.com

Abstract

Sub-Saharan African countries such as Nigeria will continue to have higher population growth. By projection, this will have the effect of contributing to over half of the global population by 2050. Nigeria being the most populous African nation is currently occupying the sixth position in population growth globally and by 2050, the country would have become the third most populous nation in the world. This paper examines the level and trend of fertility in Nigeria through in-depth scholarly papers with the intent of assessing the causes of high fertility levels and rates in Nigeria. The findings reveal that cultural and religious factors are the leading causes of high fertility behaviour in Nigeria. The paper concludes that in achieving demographic dividend for sustainable development in Nigeria, which is the main aim of the 2021 National Population Policy, there is an urgent need to address Nigeria's sustained high fertility rate which is already in momentum through: counselling, expanding access to modern family planning and promoting birth spacing. It was recommended that adequate government policies need to be put in place in addressing the various predicting factors affecting fertility in Nigeria with the aim of checking the rapid population growth rate being experienced in the country.

Keywords: *Fertility level, Trends, Behaviour, Development, Nigeria*

1.0 Introduction

Globally there is an increase in population growth rate despite a decline in fertility rate. This can be attributed to development in public health and improvement in medicine which has in turn led to reduction in mortality rates. In the demographic transition, fertility is responding to mortality. Sub-Saharan Africa will continue to have a higher population growth rate and it is expected to be over half of the global population by 2050. Nigeria being the most populous African nation is currently occupying the sixth position in population growth globally and by 2050, the country would have become the third most populous nation in the world (UNPF, 2022). Early marriage is common among women in developing countries most especially in sub-Saharan African countries like Nigeria and this has facilitated high fertility rate and level (Stephen *et al.*, 2012). The rate of increase in the total number of children-ever-born in Nigeria with a proportionate growth in the economy is very inimical to human development (Jecinta *et al.*, 2020).

Modern contraceptive use in Nigeria remains low despite socio-economic and health benefits associated with its use. Given Nigeria's commitment towards doubling contraceptive prevalence use in the country within four years, there is the need to investigate factors affecting and mediating contraceptive use behaviour so as to ensure responsive and positive results. At the community and individual level where there is female education, autonomy and access to health care facilities, there is a high percentage of contraceptive use. Communities with higher

proportions of Muslims and polygamous families showed negative results in modern contraceptive use (Adebowale, 2019; Clara *et al.*, 2015).

Nigeria is among the top 20 countries in Africa having the highest number of child brides due to child marriage attributed to deep entrenchment of this practice in the country's religion and customs. Religious and ethnic communities in the northern part of the country have the attendant effect of posing disastrous consequences on the lives of the victims including social evils and health hazards (Miriam *et al.*, 2018). There is the need to abolish child marriage in the country due to its attendant consequences. In achieving this objective, the constitution of the country need to be amended by ensuring the 18 years minimum age for marriage provided in the Child's Right Act. This act should be applicable throughout the country for customary, civil and religious marriages. There is the need for adequate registration of marriages and births through effective machinery in both rural and urban areas thereby helping the appropriate authorities in enforcing the minimum age at marriage throughout the country. Rural dwellers need to be well enlightened and educated on the health hazards associated with child marriage thereby stretching the importance and economic benefits of girl child education.

The Concept of Fertility Behaviour

Fertility is a demographic word that encompasses various components such as birth rate, which is the intensity; birth volume, which is the number of births; family planning, which involves birth spacing, and age of entry into reproduction. These variables are the essential components of the demographic word, fertility. Nigeria's current fertility rate as at 2023 is estimated at 5.076 births per woman which has declined by 1.32 percent from 2022 which was 5.144 births per woman. The fertility rate in Nigeria, which is about 5.1 births per woman, has been falling consistently from about 6.6 births per woman since 1973 to 5.1 births per woman as at 2022. The birth rate for Nigerian women as at 2022 was estimated at 36.440 births per 1000 people which presents a 1.13 percent decline from that of 2021; which was estimated at 36.855 births per 1,000 people, also presenting a 1.11 percent decline from that of 2020. The birth rate for women in Nigeria as at 2020 was estimated at 37.269 births per 1,000 people, which presents a 1.1 percent decline from that of 2019 (NPC, 2018).

From the analysis of the trend above, it can be deduced that births and fertility rates for Nigerian women have been declining consistently from 2019 till the present period. The most significant demographic change that has occurred in Nigeria in terms of fertility have been attributed to decline in fertility. This is not peculiar to Nigeria alone but all over the world. Since 1970, total fertility has been declining from 37 percent; 4.5 births per woman as at 1970s to about 2.8 as at 2000. Some other social factors prevalent in Nigeria such as low standard of living of women, lack of social mobility, joint occupation and community life, caste system and joint family have triggered the high fertility rate in Nigeria despite the global decline coupled with the fact that the Nigerian population attributed to fertility is already in a momentum. This may account for the high fertility levels in northern Nigeria when compared to the southern part of the country. These factors may also be responsible for the high fertility rate in most of the developing countries most especially sub-Saharan Africa (NPC, 2018).

Study Aim and Objectives

The aim of the study is in line with the various components of fertility, as it relates to fertility level, trends and behaviour in Nigeria. The study examines general fertility level, trends and

behaviour in Nigeria in the last five years. The specific objectives are to describe the fertility level, trends and behaviour and their associated contributory factors in Nigeria.

Fertility Levels and Trends in Nigeria

The Total Fertility Rate (TFR) as at 1990 was 6.01. As at 2013, it dropped to 5.5 and the decline has been consistent over the years. Even though Nigeria has been witnessing a decline in fertility rate since 1990, the population still keeps increasing. This could be attributed to improvement in community health care that has made natural growth rate to remain high. Studies now show that Nigeria is currently the sixth most populous country in the world and by year 2050, the country is predicted to occupy the position of the third most populous country in the world. Findings attributed the high fertility rate in Nigeria to high infant and child mortality rate – since fertility is responding to mortality, early marriage most especially in the northern Nigeria and some other south eastern part of the country, early childbearing which is mostly attributed to early marriage age of entry into reproduction. These have increased the reproductive life span of both the male and female, low use of contraception among couples and adolescents which is also mostly common in the northern part of Nigeria due to low level of education and high social values placed on child bearing. This study shows the trend of fertility decline in the last five years till the present (NPC, 2018).

Table 1: Fertility Trends in Nigeria (2017-2023)

Year	Fertility Rate	Growth Rate
2023	5.076	-1.32%
2022	5.144	-1.30%
2021	5.212	-1.31%
2020	5.281	-1.27%
2019	5.349	-1.26%
2018	5.417	-1.19%
2017	5.482	-1.15%

Source: DHS Stat Compiler

From Table 1 above, it can be deduced that the fertility rate has been declining consistently since 2017 till the present time, which is now 5.076. However, this decline does not translate to decline in population in Nigeria due to some factors highlighted earlier and also coupled with the fact that the Nigerian population is already in a momentum. Consequently, efforts towards reducing the population size may not be easily felt in the nearest future. Demographic projections forecast that Nigeria's population may keep on increasing in the next decades and by year 2050, the population

would have grown to 450 million when compared to year 2022 thereby making the country to be the third most populous country in the world. The graphical presentation is given below:

Figure 1: Fertility Trend in Nigeria (2017-2023)

From the graph (Figure 1) above, the total fertility rate (TFR) has been declining consistently from 2017 till 2023 and the present. Total Fertility Rates (TFR) and Crude Birth Rates (CBR) are measures of fertility. It is against this backdrop that it is expedient to also examine the trend of fertility decline in crude birth rate in Nigeria. According to the World Factbook, Nigeria is currently the highest country with a crude birth rate of an average annual birth of 47.28 with per 1000 people per year. The crude birth rate is an indicator of the number of live births occurring during a year per 1000 population which is estimated at midyear. The subtraction of the crude death rate from the crude birth rate gives the natural increase of the population, (natural growth rate) when ruling out the influence of migration. The table below (Table 2) depicts the decline in crude birth rate in Nigeria since 2017.

The consistent fertility decline in Total Fertility Rate (TFR) is also true for the Crude Birth Rate (CBR). From the table above, the current crude birth rate for Nigeria is estimated at 36.026 births per 1000 people which represents about 1.14 percent decline from that of 2022. That of 2022 which was estimated at 36.440 births per 1000 people also represents a 1.13 percent decline from that of 2021. That of year 2021 was estimated at 36.855 births per 1000 people which represented 1.11 percent decline from 2020 and the decline has been consistent over the years. From the graph (Figure 2), the birth rate has been declining consistently from 2017 to 2023 till present.

Factors Determining Fertility Levels and Trends in Nigeria

Studies have shown that exposure of women to the risk of child bearing through age of entry into reproduction (first marriage) is one of the most proximate determinants of fertility in Nigeria. Some of the other determinants of fertility levels in areas of birth spacing, parity and family planning are postpartum sexual abstinence and breastfeeding. This is because most societies most especially in the northern part of Nigeria prefer the natural method of family planning through

Table 2: Fertility Trend in Crude Birth Rate in Nigeria (2017-2023)

Year	Crude Birth Rate	Growth Rate
2023	36.026	-1.14%
2022	36.44	-1.13%
2021	36.855	-1.11%
2020	37.269	-1.10%
2019	37.684	-1.09%
2018	38.098	-1.25%
2017	38.582	-1.24%

Source: DHS Stat Compiler

The graphical presentation is given below:

Figure 2: Graphical Presentation of trends in birth rates (2017-2023)

postpartum abstinence and breastfeeding to the modern method with the argument that the use of such methods may have its attendant consequences and may disrupt the reproductive process (Jecinta *et al.*, 2020).

Generally, factors associated with decreased fertility level include value and attitudinal changes, most especially in the perception of family planning and modern contraception, income of couple,

education of the couple, female participation in the labour force, age, population control, contraceptive use, reluctance of partners to have children, infertility, obesity, pollution, gender equality and so forth. Since fertility is responding to mortality, other factors determining high levels of fertility in Nigeria include infant and child mortality, early childbearing and universal marriage. Variation in fertility levels is reported to be at the highest rate in the northern part of Nigeria can be addressed through improving women education most especially, the Hausa/Fulani and that it is very important to take into consideration ethnicity in fertility reduction strategies in Nigeria (Adebowale, 2019).

Age at Marriage and Fertility Behaviour in Nigeria

According to Stephen *et al.* (2012) early marriage is very common among women in developing countries, most especially Africa. Their article focused on survival analysis of age at first marriage among women of reproductive age across Nigeria and differences across regions. They assert that age at first marriage may have serious health implications on both the women involved and their children, most especially those under five years old. Emmanuel *et al.* (2018) took a step further by examining parents' perception on factors affecting early marriage in the southern part of Nigeria focusing on the Urhobos in Delta State of Nigeria. They discover that early marriage had forced girls into adulthood before they were physically and emotionally mature and which has led to drastic harmful effects on the victims' health conditions and has affected their economic, educational and social development. They suggest educational intervention and community needs assessment and conclude that factors and causes that lead to early marriages need to be identified in every society in order to address the social problem.

Miriam *et al.* (2018) posit that Nigeria is among the top 20 countries in Africa having the highest number of child brides due to child marriage attributed to deep entrenchment of this practice in the country's religion and customs and that the practice is more prevalent in religious and ethnic communities in the northern part of the country thereby posing deleterious consequences on the lives of the victims including social evils and health hazards. They conclude that rural dwellers need to be well enlightened and educated on the health hazards associated with child marriage and stretching the importance and economic benefits of girl child education. Kingley and Mudiaga, (2020) suggest that laws and provisions on early marriage within the context of marriage age should be fundamental under chapter four of the 1999 constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria and that grassroots, door-to-door campaign and multi-faceted approaches need to be adopted towards addressing the menace of child marriage in Nigeria. In northern Nigeria, adequate studies have not been conducted in examining the issue of early marriage and this is most paramount in the northern part of the country considering the low education, self-esteem of women coupled with religious doctrines attached to early marriage.

Thomas (2010) observed a significant positive relationship between religious affiliations of women and divorce rates. He recommends that social workers, helping professionals and family counsellors need to provide strategies towards solving or reducing divorce faced by Nigerian couples. Despite the fact that Ibadan is in the southwestern part of Nigeria with multi-religious groups and high literacy rate, the age of entry into reproduction is still exacting influence on fertility through divorce rates thereby suggesting intervention study in all parts of the country on the age of entry into marriage and reproduction as a factor affecting fertility in Nigeria.

Family Planning and Fertility Behaviour in Nigeria

Irit *et al.* (2020), in a study on unmet needs for family planning and contraceptive use in Kaduna posit that as at 2017, only one-fifth of all married women of reproductive age in Kaduna State experienced unmet need for contraception which have led to high risky fertility behaviours thereby compromising reproductive rights. They stress further that many women in Kaduna State suffer from lack of empowerment in making contraceptive decisions. They also assert that home barriers, community barriers and lack of health facilities has impeded the extent to which fertility desires can be achieved. They highlight normative, cultural, financial and social factors such as permission of the husband in accessing service providers, among others, as some of the factors impeding contraceptive use and accessing family planning services. They conclude that studies can be transformed into programmatic interventions towards improving voluntary use of contraceptives.

Monday *et al.* (2021) and Chinelo *et al.* (2015), in a study aimed at assessing whether men's exposure to family planning and demand-generated activities are associated with use of modern contraceptive methods. Their findings reveal city and country variations across geographical contexts and suggest gender-comprehensive and context-specific programmes in reducing unmet needs for family planning. Similarly, Olugbenga *et al.* (2022) and Clara *et al.* (2015) assert that modern contraceptive use in Nigeria remains low despite socio-economic and health benefits associated with its use. They stress further that given Nigeria's commitment towards doubling contraceptive prevalence use in Nigeria within four years, there is the need to investigate the mediating factors affecting and mediating use behaviour for various government programmes towards contraceptive use to be responsive and yield positive results. Their study reveals that overall, community and individual levels where there is female education, autonomy and access to health care facilities, there is high percentage of contraceptive use.

Emmanuel *et al.* (2010), in a study on contraceptive practices in Nigeria, acknowledge low rate of contraceptive use despite widespread sexual activity and awareness of various contraceptive methods among Nigerian youths and adolescents. They stress that there are research evidence identifying various factors that have contributed to low prevalence of modern contraceptive use in Nigeria with the most prevalent factor being the myth on the side effects of modern contraceptives. They identify lack of political will in Nigeria in providing family planning programmes on larger scale using community programmes and community-oriented approaches in changing the myths about side effects associated with use of modern contraceptives. Their review highlight concepts and methods in contraception, reasons for low contraceptive practice and use in Nigeria and need for Nigeria to generate a political priority and will towards making a change in maternal health indicators with the ultimate goal of providing direction in guiding changes in the Nigeria Population Policy as it affects family planning and contraceptive use.

Jecinta *et al.* (2020), and Mustapha and Ismaila (2006) assert that northern Nigeria remains a patrilineal society which is characterised with early age at marriage of women, that men determine contraceptive and familial fertility decisions. They suggest that willingness of husbands to allow their spouses to adopt and use family planning practices will go a long way in determining the pace of fertility reduction in Nigeria. Results of their study reveal high knowledge of contraceptive use but a generally negative attitude towards limiting family size for economic reasons and consequently low rates of contraceptive use. They stress that respondents who showed positive interest towards contraceptive use were more willing to use contraceptives for child spacing than limiting family size. They conclude that attitudes of men regarding decisions are very important on decisions regarding contraceptive use since knowledge of

contraception is already high among respondents who use and don't use it. Consequently, family planning programmes that focused mainly on women will continue to achieve limited success in northern Nigeria and other patrilineal societies where similar programmes are pursued.

Parity of Children and Fertility Behaviour in Nigeria

Olugbenga *et al.* (2022) posit that strategies in reducing Nigeria's population growth rate are yet to yield positive impacts as fertility preferences remain high among women of reproductive age. Most women of reproductive age in Nigeria still give birth to more than four children recommended by the national policy. They stress that other predictors of fertility intentions are children-ever-born, number of living children and fertility intentions. They conclude that having four children may not be compatible with the desired level of fertility for women due to the factors highlighted above and they recommend proper advocacy on economic and social desirable fertility levels for women. Similarly, Irit *et al.* (2020) and Adebowale *et al.* (2011) assert that high frequency of childbearing coupled with short birth spacing have the tendency of affecting maternal health through maternal depletion syndrome. They recommend in their study that strategies need to be adopted in improving women's knowledge on the effect of short birth spacing on maternal health. Their study is relevant to this discourse because maternal health has a direct relationship with fertility rate of women of reproductive age. The healthier women are, the better fertility outcomes to be experienced.

In a similar vein, Stephen *et al.* (2011) discover that parity progression from parity 0 to 4 is consistently higher among never-users than women who ever used contraception. They also discovered that completed fertility was significantly higher among never-users of contraceptives. Their discovery buttressed the fact that contraceptive use is still low in various parts of the country despite the health benefits associated with birth spacing and family planning. A conclusion can invariably be drawn that there is the need for continuous examination of various intervening variables that might have hindered the usage with a view to allowing various government programmes yield positive results.

2.0 Methodology

The methodology used for this paper is an in depth review of scholarly papers and articles, based on the general and specific objectives of the paper. The search engine used for this paper was Google scholar. The keywords used for the electronic search are in accordance with the specific objectives of the study. Some of the literature found in the Google scholar were also in the Pubmed and other academic search databases. Meanings and definitions of concepts relating to fertility levels, trends and behaviour were accessed from the internet and Nigeria Demography and Health Survey (NDHS).

The current fertility levels and trends in Nigeria were measured through the Total Fertility Rate (TFR) and Crude Birth Rates (CBR) and were also accessed from the NDHS and internet. The determinants of fertility behaviour in Nigeria were assessed through the specific objectives which are: age of entry into reproduction and marriage among couples as possible determinant of fertility levels, trends and behaviour in Nigeria, practice of family planning in terms of contraceptive use and birth spacing among couples as possible determinant of fertility trends and behaviour in Nigeria, and parity of children attributed to every couple as possible determinants of fertility levels, trends and behaviour in Nigeria.

3.0 Discussion of Results

Results of the study shall be in line with the objectives of the study; grounded in the literatures and deductions from other data sources. With the Total Fertility Rate (TFR) of 6.01 in 1990 and which has been consistently reducing till present, which is estimated at 5.076 for 2023, there is no gainsaying that Nigeria has been witnessing a decline in fertility rate since 1990 despite the fact that the population still keeps increasing. This could be attributed to improvement in medicine that has kept the natural growth rate to remain high. Nigeria is currently the country with the highest crude birth rate with an average annual birth rate of 47.28 with per 1000 people per year as at 2023 which has also been declining since 1990. The high fertility rate in Nigeria can be attributed to high infant and child mortality rate; since fertility is responding to mortality. The high fertility level in Nigeria despite the fact that the fertility rate has been declining since 1990 can be attributed to early marriage most especially in northern Nigeria and some other south eastern part of the country.

Impediments to family planning and other birth prevention strategies put in place by the Nigerian government can be attributed to religious and cultural barriers most especially as regarding the importance placed child bearing coupled with the fact that the Nigerian population is already in momentum and positive effects of these measures and strategies by the government; National population policies cannot be easily felt in the nearest future. By regions in Nigeria, early marriage is mostly associated with the northern part of Nigeria and this explains the high fertility rate in the northern part of the country when compared to other regions such as the south western part of the country. Early marriage in the northern part of Nigeria can also be attributed to the low education status of women, high importance attached to childbearing and having families, cultural practices of giving the girl child in marriage and religious believes attributed to early marriage most especially the Islamic importance of giving the girl child in hands to her husband for marriage early.

The practice of family planning in terms of contraceptive use and birth spacing among couples as possible determinant of fertility trends and behaviour in Nigeria reveals that the practice of family planning among couples in terms of contraceptive use and birth spacing among couples in Nigeria still leaves much to be desired most especially in the northern part of the country. This is because of some cultural beliefs on contraceptive use that it is affecting the natural process of reproduction. Also, some cultures attach more importance to having large families with the belief that they can be of assistance in farm work and can compensate the parents at their old age. Some cultures prefer natural methods of family planning such as postpartum abstinence rather than use of contraceptive devices with the belief that use of such modern methods may have its attendant negative effect on the couple, most especially the women.

Parity of children attributed to every couple as possible determinant of fertility levels, trends and behaviour in Nigeria showed that strategies in reducing Nigeria population growth rate are yet to yield positive impacts as fertility preferences remain high among women of reproductive age as most Nigerian women of reproductive age in Nigeria are still giving birth to more than four children recommended by the national policy. The use of modern contraception in Nigeria is still low most especially in the northern part of Nigeria. Some religious beliefs may not support some of the modern methods such as sterilization and would rather throw more weight on the modern methods such as prolonged natural breastfeeding and postpartum abstinence. This can explain why fertility levels still remain high in the northern part of Nigeria when compared to other regions of the country such as the south west. In Demography, family planning is a very

important fertility variable that determines parity, birth spacing and even children-ever-born to a particular woman.

4.0 Conclusion

From discussions so far, there is no gainsaying that fertility level and rate in Nigeria is still at high level despite government policies and programmes towards reducing the trend. This can be attributed to cultural factors such as high importance placed on child bearing, polygamy family structure, early marriage and religious factors such as having a negative thought on use of modern contraception with the argument of some of its attendant negative consequences such as disrupting the natural process of reproduction and throwing more weight on natural methods of birth spacing such as natural breastfeeding and postpartum abstinence. In achieving demographic dividend for sustainable development in Nigeria, which is the main aim of the 2021 National Population Policy, there is an urgent need to address Nigeria's sustained high fertility rate which is already in momentum through counselling, expanding access to modern family planning and promoting birth spacing. Based on these findings and similar findings, it is recommended that adequate government policies need to be in place in addressing the various predicting factors affecting fertility in Nigeria with the aim of checking the rapid population growth rate we are experiencing in the country.

References

- be FA, (2011). Child spacing and parity progression: implication for maternal nutritional status among women in Ekiti communities, south western Nigeria. *Pakistan journal of nutrition* 10(5), 485-491.
- Adebowale, Stephen A., Francis A Fagbemigbe, Elijah A Bamgboye, (2011). Contraceptive use: Implication for completed fertility, parity progression and maternal nutritional status in Nigeria. *African journal of reproductive health* 15(4), 60-67.
- Adebowale, Stephen A., Francis A Fagbemigbe, Titus O Okareh, Ganiyu O, (2012). Survival analysis of timing of first marriage among women of reproductive age in Nigeria: regional differences. *A journal of reproductive health* 16(4) 95-107.
- Adebowale, Stephen A., (2019). Ethnic disparities in fertility and its determinants in Nigeria. *Fertility research and practice*. Article number 3.
- Adegoke, Thomas Gbadegbo (2010). Socio-cultural factors as determinants of divorce rates among women of reproductive age in Ibadan metropolis, Nigeria. *Study of tribes and tribals* 8(2), 107-114.
- Babalola, Stella, Olamide Oyenubi, Mojisola Odeku, (2017). Factors affecting the achievement of fertility intentions in Urban Nigeria: analysis of longitudinal data. *BMC Public Health*.
- Efout, Monday Richmond, Amarachi Chiagoziem, (2021). Paternity Fraud: Examining its causes, Tort of Deceit and Victims Compensation GSJ 9(12).
- Ejembi, Clara Ladi, Tukur Dahiru, Alhaji A Aliyu, (2015). Contextual factors influencing modern contraceptive use in Nigeria. *DHS working papers*.

4th African Institute for Science Policy and Innovation Biennial International Conference Proceedings

- Emmanuel A Agege, Ezekiel U Nwose, Stella Odjemogbo, (2018). Parents' perception on factors of early marriage among the Urhobos in Delta State of Nigeria. *International journal of community medicine and public health* 5(2), 411-415.
- Emmanuel Monjok, Andrea Smesny, John E Ekabna, E James Essien, (2010). Contraceptive practices in Nigeria: Literature review and recommendation for future policy decisions. *Open access journal of contraception*.
- Irit Sinal, Elizabeth Omoluabi, Adenike Jimoh, Kaja Jurczynska, (2020). Unmet needs for family planning and barriers to contraceptive use in Kaduna, Nigeria: Culture, myths and perceptions. *Culture, health & sexuality* 22(11), 1253-1268.
- Ibeji Jecinta U., Temesgen Zewotir, Delia North, Lateef Amusa, (2020). Modelling fertility levels in Nigeria using Generalised Poisson Regression-based approach. *Scientific African Journal*.
- Miriam Chinyere Anozie, Millicent Ele, Elizabeth Ijeamaka Anika, (2018). The legal, medical and social implications of child marriage in Nigeria. *International journal of law, policy and the family* 32(2), 119-139.
- Mrabure, Kingsley O, Mudiaga K. Ovakporae, (2020). Unabated menace of child marriage in Nigeria. The need for an enabling constitutional provision. *JL Policy & Globalisation* 98, 179.
- Mustapha C Duze, Ismaila Z Mohammed, (2006). Male knowledge, attitude and family planning practice in northern Nigeria. *African journal of reproductive health* 10(3), 53-65.
- National Population Census (2018) Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey Data Set (NDHS 2018).
- Olaseinde, Olugbenga Sunday, Olusola Gabriel Owagbemi, Justina Olufunke, (2022). Fertility intentions among high-parity women in Nigeria: How satisfying are four living children. *Journal of population and social studies JPSS* 30, 488-507.
- United Nations, (2022). World population prospectus. *27th edition, Nov 15*.